

ISic2969

I.Sicily inscription 2969

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palazzolo Acreide, Museo Iudica, inventory 2252

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI175466

1. [— — —]#⁷#⁷ων λυπη [— — —]
2. [— — —] ζήσας χαρι [— — —]
3. [— — — — —].I P,Λ [— — — —]
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645325

PHI 175466

Bibliography

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1959.0546

Pugliese Carratelli, G. 1956. Silloge dell' epigrafi acrensi. In Bernabó Brea, L.

(eds.), *Akrai*. Catania. pp. 151-181. At no.33 ph

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2969. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387815>